

Protoriboceptors

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How cells, organelles, and organisms communicate and sense their environment is a fundamental question in biology with implications ranging from cancer to planetary homeostasis. The identity of endogenous, *in vivo* gas-sensing nucleic acids are still unknown.¹⁻⁴ I recently proposed the term riboceptors and deoxyriboceptor for all the RNAs and DNA molecules that can “sense” any biomolecule or factor. Additionally, several theoretical models of gas- and temperature-sensing riboceptors were also proposed that can be extended to sensing any other type of molecules or factors.^{4,5} In protein-based gasoreceptors (such as DosP, CooA or sGC), the presence of multiple domains suggests an evolutionary advanced development in sensing mechanisms related to evolutionarily old molecules such as gases.^{2,4} During evolution, proteins with simpler or less domains too must have had the ability to sense evolutionarily old molecules, and such mechanisms must also be potentially conserved in vertebrates and plants. The signaling due to such receptors may be classified under split-component or proto-component signal transduction systems.^{6,7} Hemoglobin and its paralogs can be considered an example of split- or even proto-component signal transduction system and one of its roles may include roles as gasoreceptors and/or protogasoreceptors.⁸⁻¹⁰ However, if hemoglobin can be considered as a protogasoreceptor, this warrants a revision on the existing theoretical models of riboceptors that seem to be only based on RNA or DNA-based split-component and one-component signal transduction systems.^{4,5} Therefore, to supplement the existing riboceptors models, an additional protoriboceptor (and protodeoxyriboceptor) model is proposed as an example of a nucleic acid-based proto-component signal transduction system. Finally, it is challenging to ignore the possibility of nucleic acids and proteins cooperatively performing sensing and signaling roles, respectively, or vice versa. As the diversity of ribonucleoproteins are extremely complex, considering these models will be essential to understand some of the complexities of gasocrine signaling.

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